

ISSUES IN MODELING DISCONTINUOUS RANDOM FIBER SRIM COMPOSITES

O. Ochoa and T. Eason

*Center for Mechanics of Composites, Texas A&M University,
College Station, Texas, 77840-3123, USA*

SUMMARY: The performance of SRIM (Structural Reaction Injection Molded) composites with thermal spray preform is simulated with finite element analysis and compared to experimental data. The finite element method is used in conjunction with an idealized representative volume element (RVE) to develop an understanding of the fiber/fiber and fiber/matrix behavior. A one dimensional transient heat transfer analysis is used to simulate the thermal gradient through the thickness of the RVE to simulate the processing stresses. Once the residual stresses are introduced into the RVE model, the tangent tensile modulus is calculated for the RVE. The emphasis is placed on the thermomechanical response and the accompanying degradation in strength and stiffness. The RVE methodology will be used to understand the effects of the fiber/fiber interaction and matrix behavior on the static properties of the composite. Initial results indicate that the approach taken provides a realistic avenue to access the micro and macro aspects of this material system.

KEYWORDS: discontinuous fiber, residual stresses from processing, structural reaction injection molding, thermomechanical modeling, damage initiation and progression

INTRODUCTION

Adequate analysis of the processing effects on the mechanical performance becomes of increasing importance as more economical manufacturing options are sought for composites. Randomly oriented discontinuous fiber (RDF) composites provide one avenue for reducing manufacturing cost by combining high production rates with low material cost and scrap rates. Empirical relations for the modulus of RDF composites work well for predicting the mechanical response in the initial region. However, experimental evidence suggests that SRIM composites display a non-linear stress-strain response. The experimental observations may be validated by investigating the interaction among neighboring fibers and between the fiber and matrix under thermomechanical loading. This is accomplished by using a finite element model with non-linear matrix properties and damage progression capability to characterize the non-linear response of the composite and identify of the failure mode. Improvements in material performance can then be obtained by adjusting the influential material parameters for improved performance of the composite system.

Experiments to understand the influence of the fiber structure have concentrated on parametric studies to determine the influence of chop length, strand size and binder type on the permeability of the preform and structural performance of the composite. From these studies, the important fiber parameters are identified as binder type and number of filaments per a strand. Chop length (when varied well above the critical length) and filament diameter

appear to have little influence on the modulus and strength of the composite. The important matrix properties are coefficient of thermal expansion, modulus and yield strength. Matrix ductility has been shown to have little influence on the performance of the composite system .

The prediction of modulus and strength using a laminate analogy is adequate for predicting the response of the composite at the macro level. Early work formed the quasi-isotropic laminate analogy which provided a good approximation for the initial linear modulus. Current research in random fiber composites continues to rely on laminate analogy but addresses fiber orientation and progressive failure to capture the nonlinear response. This type of development is limited because fiber/matrix interface and fiber/fiber interaction are only accounted for in a smeared manner. The micro-mechanical aspects of the fiber/matrix interface and fiber/fiber interaction appear to be the most promising in developing a complete picture of the RDF SRIM composite's behavior. A shear lag approach to investigate the stresses around a short fiber imbedded in a matrix has contributed to the understanding of the load transfer within discontinuous fibrous composites. This approach works well for aligned fiber composites. However for fibrous assemblies where the fibers come into contact with one another, the axial fiber stress and the interfacial shear stress at the outer fiber surface is difficult to predict. The most promising path in developing a thorough understanding of the failure behavior of the RDF SRIM composite's behavior is to account for the constituents distinctive structure within the micromechanics frame.

The micromechanics approach introduces higher order stress or strain gradients to account for heterogeneity in the material system. Internal strain energy of the system can be used to obtain average of the stress-strain variations in the composite leading to the stiffness or compliance evaluation. It is extremely important to describe the structure of the heterogeneity as closely as possible to generate accurate results. Improved bounds for the moduli can be obtained using information beyond that contained in the volume fraction as in rule of mixtures. Komori and Makishima developed a general expression for the average number of contacts per unit fiber length in randomly oriented fibrous assemblies which was later improved by Pan. These contacts are believed to be essential in the understanding of the structural heterogeneity in the material for RDF composite systems.

PROCESSING AND EXPERIMENTAL OBSERVATIONS

The thermal spray/SRIM process begins by manufacturing a near net shape fiber preform. The fiber preform is constructed on a wire screen with an exhaust fan connected to one end. A continuous roving spool is used to deliver the strand to the chopper gun where the roving is cut into two inch lengths. As the two inch strand leaves the chopper gun, the strand crosses paths with a flame gun and a stream of binder melting the binder to the strand before being delivered to the preform screen. The binder quickly solidifies and holds the fiber to the preform. The exhaust fan is used to pull air over the fibers to hold them in place while the binder cools. The preform is then removed from the screen and ready for injection molding. After the fiber preform is constructed, the preform is inserted into a mold cavity. The mold cavity is closed and the preform is injected with a fast reacting two part polyurethane system at a mold temperature of 93°C. After the panel is cured for approximately 90 seconds, the mold is opened and the composite panel is removed and cooled down to room temperature. As the surface begins to cool, it takes on a tensile in-plane stresses while the warmer interior assumes a compressive state of in-plane normal stress. As the center reaches room temperature, the in-plane normal stress at the surface changes sign becoming compressive

while the stresses in the interior becomes tensile. Large in-plane tensile stresses develop due to the mismatch in the thermal coefficients of expansion between the glass fiber reinforcement and the urethane resin during cooling giving rise to areas that will favor yielding and microcracking.

Photoelastic results verify that residual stresses in the plane of the fibers are of a substantial tensile magnitude within the resin. Estimates of the difference between the in-plane stress and the through the thickness stress range from 6.4 -12.7 MPa at points in the matrix away from the fibers. If the through the thickness stress is assumed to be negligible, the in-plane stress in the matrix becomes 6.4- 12.7 MPa. The worst case occurs if the resin is not allowed to contract in the through the thickness direction implying that the in-plane stress in the matrix could be as high as 18.8-24.8 MPa which is about 30% of the yield stress in the matrix.

SPATE 9000 (interferometry) observations during tensile-tensile fatigue testing indicates that the damage displayed in the test coupon originates from localized region within the specimen. The regions appear as low stress areas and grow as fatigue cycles accumulate as shown in Fig. 1. Notice the region between 40 to 45 mm where the spot at 7 thousand cycles grows as the number of cycles increases. This is the location where the test specimen failed. The rest of the test specimen shows a variation of stresses that increases as cycles accumulate. The lower portion (0-10 mm) shows the influence of the bottom grip. When the specimen was measured with a non-contact thermometer, the temperature was higher at the 40 to 45 mm location than other regions within the specimen. This indicates the hysteresis in the material was greater at the damage sites. It is believed the heat production at the 40 to 45 mm region indicates the presence of yielding, microcracking and interphase damage.

Fig. 1: Progressive failure of a tensile fatigue specimen using SPATE (40% ult. R=.1)

The stress-strain response of the static tensile specimen displays two moduli at room temperature as shown in Fig. 2. The initial modulus is 12.1 GPa with the secondary modulus at 7.89 GPa. Even though the initial part of the curve appears to be linear, a slight softening is present at lower stresses. This is attributed to matrix yielding and microcracking at localized regions in the specimen that is verified by photoelastic observations. These localized regions

are initiated during processing as the composite cools from 200°F to 70°F and influence the mechanical performance of the composite.

Fig. 2: Static tensile response of RDF SRIM composites at room temperature

EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

Mechanical properties for the neat resin were determined as a function of temperature. Static testing for the neat resin followed ASTM D3039 for tensile and ASTM D3410 for compression. The yield stress for the neat resin was determined using Considere's method where the tangent point to the true stress versus extension ratio curve is found that passes through zero extension ratio. The material displays an elastic perfectly plastic behavior. Data obtained from uniaxial tension and compression tests at four temperatures are tabulated in Table 1. The modulus of the resin in Fig. 3 was determined using a Rheometrics RSAII Solids Analyzer with a temperature sweep conducted at 1 Hz. Variations in the coefficient of linear thermal expansion in Fig. 3 were found using a Rheometrics TMA.

The thermal properties of the composite were required for the transient heat transfer analysis to predict the residual stresses from processing. A Mettler DSC 30 was used to obtain specific heat as a function of temperature. The average value between the mold temperature and room temperature was found to be 1.01 J/(gram*K). The thermal conductance of the composite material was determined to be 431.5 Jm/(Hr*m² °C) using a Dynatech Rapid-K with the upper plate set at 40 °C and the lower plate set at 6 °C.

Static tensile test for the composite followed ASTM D5083. The primary modulus, E_1 , was obtained from the initial linear portion of the stress versus strain curve as per ASTM D5083. The secondary modulus, E_2 , was obtained by linear regression through the last half of the stress strain curve.

Table 1: Yield stress for tensile and compression tests at various temperatures

Temperature °C	Tensile MPa	Compressive MPa
-40	98.6	101.3
21	77.1	77.8
49	53.0	54.3
78	35.3	34.2

Fig. 3: Modulus and coefficient of linear thermal expansion of the resin as a function of temperature

COMPUTATIONAL MODELING

Finite element method is used in conjunction with an RVE to predict the performance of the composite. Residual stresses from processing are modeled using a one dimensional transient heat transfer analysis to simulate the thermal gradient through the thickness of the part. Constant strain boundary conditions are applied to the RVE so that the average constitutive response for the composite can be determined with and without residual stresses. The model uses one dimensional continuum elements to simulate the fibers and three dimensional continuum elements to represent the resin. The glass fibers are assumed to remain linearly elastic until failure. The resin is modeled as a nonlinear isotropic material within ABAQUS. The Hencky-Mises criterion is used as the matrix yield criteria for elastic perfectly plastic behavior. A model of this type is extremely useful due to its simplicity and computational efficiency while still providing an approximation to the variation in the microstructure.

MESH/DISCRETIZATION

The finite element model of the RVE consists of three layers of fibers representing one tenth of the thickness of the panel thickness. The RVE mesh is constructed by first generating the resin region and then adding the fibers. Three dimensional continuum elements, C3D8 in ABAQUS, are used to represent the resin system and one dimensional continuum elements, C1D2 in ABAQUS, are used to represent the fiber. The fiber angles and locations are randomly assigned within planes orthogonal to the Z axis. Multi-point constraints are used to attach the fibers to the resin. If the fiber node occupies the same location as a resin node, *TIE is used within ABAQUS. This makes the resin node the master node while the fiber node becomes the slave node as shown in Fig. 4 as Case I. If the fiber node is in-between two resin nodes, *LINEAR is utilized within ABAQUS. This requires the displacements for the fiber node to be linearly interpolated from the two resin nodes as shown in Fig. 4 as Case II. If the angle between the fiber and the x-axis is greater than 45° , the interpolation is accomplished between the adjacent x-nodes as shown for fiber C in Fig. 4. Fibers that are oriented less than 45° with the x-axis are interpolated between adjacent y-nodes as shown for fiber B. This insures that the maximum discrepancy between the largest possible element length is less than the square root of two times the smallest fiber element length.

Fig. 4: Fiber and resin node arrangement in mesh

BOUNDARY AND LOADING CONDITIONS

The boundary conditions are applied to the mesh in Fig. 5 are zero displacement along;

- X-axis in the Y direction,
- Y-axis in the X direction,
- and the bottom in the Z direction,

to simulate the boundary conditions for the RVE. The remaining sides in Fig. 5 are constrained using multi-point constraints to allow the;

- XX side to move in a uniform X direction,

- YY side to move in a uniform Y direction,
 - top side to move in a uniform Z direction,
- to simulate the boundary conditions for the RVE. For the thermal cool down, no other boundary conditions are applied. Thus the RVE is allowed to contract freely in a uniform fashion. The thermal gradient through the thickness is governed by a one dimensional transient heat transfer model. The RVE is assumed to be in the horizontal position with respect to the X-Y plane with convection cooling only. The composite panel is assumed to be stress free before the RVE begins to cool. A prescribed displacement is applied to the XX-side to simulate mechanical loading. For the combined analysis of processing stresses followed by mechanical loading, a two step loading procedure is used where the RVE is cooled to room temperature and followed by the mechanical loading.

Fig. 5: Boundary conditions for the model

RESULTS

The middle layer of the mesh is shown in Fig. 6 where a fiber of interest is shown in bold with element numbers 50402-50415. The stresses shown in Fig. 7 are from thermal loading from 93 °C to 21 °C for a single fiber and multi-fiber case. The single fiber case is for the entire RVE model to contain only the fiber of interest. The multi-fiber case is when all the fibers are present in the RVE. The axial stress is obtained from the FEM analysis and is displayed as a solid line. The average interfacial stresses were calculated from the axial stress using the relationship;

$$\tau_i = -\frac{D}{4} \frac{d\sigma_f}{dx} \quad (1)$$

and is shown as a dotted line. Where $d\sigma_f/dx$ was taken to be the slope of the axial fiber stress

with respect to an incremental length of fiber and D is the diameter of the fiber. The assumption is made that there is no stress transferred at the fiber ends. Notice that the single fiber model over predicts the axial stress in the fiber by a factor of three and the shear stress at the ends of the fiber by a factor of four. This is due to the constraint from neighboring fibers in the multi-fiber case which keeps the resin from contracting and the fiber from developing the stresses shown in the single fiber case.

Fig. 6: Middle layer of the mesh with a fiber of interest shown in bold

Fig. 7: Fiber stress from single fiber and multi-fiber model with thermal loading (□ multi-fiber • single fiber)

The Mises stress for the resin from the middle layer of the multi-fiber with thermal loading only is shown in Fig. 8. For the single fiber model the Mises stresses in the resin are less than 1 MPa. When mechanical loading is applied to the model after cool down, approximately 50% of the resin is yielding at .6% strain. At 1.1 % strain more than 90% of the resin is yielding. The influence of yielding is seen in the stress versus strain curve for the RVE in Fig.

9. Notice that the FEM model without processing stresses greatly over predicts the stresses as compared to the test data and displays 48% difference in the secondary modulus with a 3% difference in the initial modulus. The FEM model with processing stresses comes closer to the actual test data with a 18% difference in the secondary modulus and a 1.6% difference in the initial modulus. The point where the stress-strain curve transitions from the initial modulus to the secondary modulus is close to .4% strain in the test data. The FEM model with processing stresses and no processing stress transitions at .5% strain. This may be attributed to flaws from processing that initiate yielding at a lower strain than is seen in the current FEM models. Current efforts are focused on developing methods to introduce processing flaws into the model to statistically simulate the distribution seen in the SRIM composite.

Fig. 8: Mises stress in the composite as processed (only resin elements shown)

CONCLUSIONS

The finite element model developed to understand RDF SRIM composites predicts large residual tensile stresses in the matrix from the processing temperature. This creates localized areas favorable to yielding within the matrix. The model is able to capture the overall non-linear response of the composite as well as fiber/fiber and fiber/matrix interaction in RDF composites. The modeling procedure appears to be realistic to investigate the thermomechanical performance of the RDF SRIM composite.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author wishes to acknowledge the financial support of The Dow Chemical Company. Particular thanks are extended to K. Fielder, J. Barron, and the B1608 Composite Test Lab for their patience and assistance.

Fig. 9: Comparison between FEM model and testing data.

REFERENCES

1. Corum, M., H. McCoy, M. Ruggles, and W. Simpson, "Durability of a Continuous Strand Mat Polymeric Composite for Automotive Structural Applications", Proceedings of the 11th Annual ESD Advanced Comp. Conf., Dearborn, MI, Nov. 1995, pp. 401-412.
2. Schell, P. L. and J. M. DiMario, "Fiber Directed Preform Reinforcement: Factors That May Influence Mechanical Properties in Liquid Composite Molding", 46th Annual Conf., Comp. Inst., The Society of Plastics Industry, February 18-21, 1991, pp. 1-7 Session 14-F.
3. Agarwal, B. D. and L. J. Broutman, Analysis and Performance of Fiber Composites, 2nd ed., John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1990. pp. 136-140.
4. Halpin, J. C. and N. J. Pagano, "The Laminate Approximation for Randomly Oriented Fibrous Composites", J. Comp. Mat., 3 pp. 720-724
5. Giurgiutiu, Victor, Kenneth Reifsnider and Ronald Kriz, "Advanced Models for Strength of Quasi-Random Fiber Composites", AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC 35th Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conf., April 18-22, 1994
6. Young, R. J., C. Galiotis, and D. N. Batchelder, "Measurement of Fibre Strain in All-Polymer Composites, 6th Int. Conf. on Deformation, Yield and Fracture, Cambridge, UK.
7. Torquato S. 1992. "Connection Between Morphology and Effective Properties of Heterogeneous Materials," ASME, AMD-Vol. 147, pp. 53-65.
8. Komori, Takashi and Kunio Makishima, "Numbers of Fiber-to-Fiber Contacts in General Fiber Assemblies", Textile Res. J. 47, (1977)
9. Pan, Ning, "A Modified Analysis of the Microstructural Characteristics of General Fiber Assemblies", Textile Research Journal, 63, 6, (1993)